

TOOLS AND METHODS TO INCREASE THE ENDURANCE OF FOOTBALL REFEREES

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Abstract. This article provides information on how to determine the rapid endurance of football assistant referees, through which the physical preparedness of referees is compared to the international requirements.

Keywords: football, referee, endurance, sports, meter, speed, field.

Аннотация. В данной статье приводится информация о том, как определить быструю выносливость футбольных помощников судей, с помощью которой физическая подготовленность судей сравнивается с международными требованиями.

Ключевые слова: футбол, судья, выносливость, спорт, метр, скорость, поле.

Nowadays, the pace of the football game is increasing. The reason for this can be attributed to the expansion of the physical capabilities of the players. Because the increase in the physical capacity of the players increases the speed of movement on the field, and thus ensures a quick view of the game processes. This factor also places specific demands on the movement activities of football referees. (1,2)

First of all, the refereeing action depends on the actions of the players during the game, and the image of the game determines the amount of movement of the referee. If the referee does not have a high level of physical training, he will not be able to physically reach the situation in the game and will have problems in accurately assessing the situation. (3,4)

For this reason, the physical fitness of referees should always be high. To do this, it is necessary to take into account this factor in the design of microcycles in the preparatory stages of the judges. An analysis of the scientific literature has shown that there are scientific studies that reflect the movement performance of football referees, but the development of physical fitness, including the use of endurance tools and the development of optimal indicators of their improvement and regulation have not been developed. There is almost no research in this area in our country, and now there is a great need for research in this area.

In order to solve the above problem, we conducted a pedagogical experiment aimed at increasing the endurance of football referees of the 1st and 2nd categories. In this experiment, 2 judges were selected. Involving the judges in this practice, special attention was paid to their age and category.

The purpose of the work. Increasing the special endurance of different categories of referees.

To achieve this goal, the Yo-Yo and 7x5 tests were first used to determine the endurance quality of the referees. This test is for referees only and is performed on the field.

In this case, a certain time is set in the range of different colored tiles, and in this time interval it is necessary to cover a distance of 20 m. In the 7x5 test, the judges will have to cover a distance of 50 meters 7 times.

As for the analysis of the test results of the chief judges, A.Nadjafaliev initially recorded a result of 61 s in the 7x50 test, while after the study he showed a result of 59 seconds. The results of the remaining judges are as follows: I. Ismailov 65 s (64 s), R.Choriev 60s (61s), A.Rahimov 66s (63s), A.Khudoyberganov 65s (64s), T.Suyunov 69s (65s), F.Norsafarov 62s (63s), E. Tursunov 62s (60s), R.Lutfulin 63s (62s). These results show that the judges Choriev and Nodirov's results in the 7x50 test decreased by 1 second, and the results increased in all other judges. (Table 1)

According to the results of the "YO-YO" test, A.Nadjafaliev initially recorded a distance of 740 m, but after the study, this figure improved to 80 m and showed a distance of 560 m. Ismailov's test result was 840 meters, and after the study the figure was 960 meters (+ 120m). The results of the remaining referees were as follows: R.Choriev 640m (+80m), A.Rahimov 540m (+80m), A.Khudoyberganov 640m (+40m), T.Suyunov 560m (+40m), F.Norsafarov 440 meters (520m), E.Tursunov 420 meters (+100), R.Lutfulin 660 meters (+ 40m). According to this test, only in Shukrullaev the result was initially 580 meters, then 540 meters, that is, the result was a decrease.

Indicators for determining the specific endurance of different categories of referees

1- table

	Full name	categories	7x50 meters (sec)		YO-YO test (m)		The difference	
			T.o	T.к	T.o	T.к	7x50 meters (sec)	YO-YO test (m)
	N-v	1	61	59	740	820	2	80
	I-v	1	65	64	840	960	1	120
	Ch-v	1	60	61	640	720	-1	80
	R-v	1	66	63	540	620	3	80
	X-v	2	65	64	640	680	1	40
	S-v	1	69	65	560	600	4	40
	Sh-v	2	59	58	580	540	1	-40
	N-v	1	62	63	440	520	-1	80
	T-v	2	62	60	420	520	2	100
	R-n	1	63	62	660	700	1	40

Reliable growth of results is related to the effectiveness of research methods and tools. The experience of these judges in improving the training load during the training period and optimizing the volume and intensity indicators has served to increase the special training of judges.

In this case, a special training phase of judges (4 weeks) was applied to different microcycles (4). The main task of the special training phase is to prepare the body for long and strong loads. It is characterized by a more intense transition from volumetric training. The training process focused on developing the body's specific endurance, aerobic and anaerobic glycolytic capabilities.

Each microcycle includes two main exercises, two auxiliary and one aerobic direction, two days of rest and the following exercises: long-term performance at the same and variable tempo, working in segments in the mixed power supply mode, running tempo, running in anaerobic mode, sprinter running, special situation exercises. In the fourth week, it was decided to reduce the amount and intensity of training and organize rehabilitation.

During the training of judges, special endurance training was organized in the following way: focus on training in the aerobic recovery zone (heart rate up to 140 beats / min); training - in the zone of aerobic development (heart rate up to 160 beats / min); The main exercises performed with continuous and intermittent large-scale exercise methods include: long running at a flat speed

with a heart rate in the range of 150-170 beats / min; running at a distance of 20-80 m with maximum and maximum speed; various jumps and strength exercises of speed-strength character.

In conclusion, it is necessary to strictly define the training program for the development of special endurance of referees. showed the effect of an experiment aimed at standing.

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